

DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING SMART SENSOR SIGNALS

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SUMMARY

The Piezo polymer and AE sensors were used for monitoring high-velocity impact damage initiation and propagation in composite laminates. A series of high-velocity impact tests were performed on the air gun impact tester. FEA is also performed to compare the damage initiation, failure mode, and extent of damage with the measured sensor signals.

Keywords: high-velocity impact, composite laminates, PVDF sensor, acoustic emission, impact damage

INTRODUCTION

The composite structures are susceptible to damage from low and high-velocity impact, which can produce significant subsurface damages while leaving little or no external visible evidence. Furthermore, it is often difficult to detect impact damage by conventional methods. Therefore, a health monitoring system for aircraft structures should include the ability to detect impact events and damage they cause [1].

The high-velocity impact such as bird strike, a hailstorm, a small piece of tire or stone during high taxing, and a piece of engine's fan blade, can cause severe damage to the structures and sub-system in spite of a very small mass. A wide variety of damage modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage in composites can be easily induced by the high-velocity impact. Several techniques for monitoring the low-velocity impact response of composite structure with sensors were proposed by many researchers [2-7]. According to Lih [3], stress wave were strongly influenced by the nature of the force history during impact process. Guo et al. [4] examined that the guided waves due to micro-fracture in composite laminates can be detected by surface mounted sensors and the characteristics of the waves are strongly related to the nature of the fracture process. Sung et al. [5] investigated the characteristics of impact damage of quasi-isotropic laminates using the wavelet analysis. Park et al. [6] showed the possibility for the monitoring of low-velocity impact damage initiation of Gr/Ep panel using piezoelectric thin film sensor. Shih et al. [7] showed the acoustic emission(AE) signal carry important information regarding the nature of the impact process using spectral analysis. However, the application of localized damage detection and

assessment of composite structures, especially high-velocity impact damage is still in its infancy. The alternative method to monitor high-velocity impact damage is to detect stress wave due to impact damage using sensor signals[8,9,10].

In this study, the PVDF(polyvinylidene fluoride) film sensors and AE transducers were used for monitoring high-velocity impact damage initiation and propagation in composite laminates to illustrate their potential benefit for structural health monitoring. A series of high-velocity impact tests were performed on the air gun impact tester to monitor the stress wave signals relevant to failure modes such as matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage. The wavelet transform and short time Fourier transform are used to decompose PVDF sensor signals in this study. The numerical analysis (FEA) is also performed to compare the damage initiation, failure mode, and extent of damage with the measured sensor signals. The extent of the damage in each case was examined by means of a conventional ultrasonic C-scan as well as a digital microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

High Velocity Impact Test

The experimental set-up and specimen are shown in Fig. 1. The specially fabricated compressed air gun impact tester was used to fire a 6.5mm diameter(1.1gr) steel ball at various impact velocities on to the composite panel. The facility consists of a compressor, pressurized air tank, gun barrel, high precision laser sensor for measuring the steel ball velocity, and supporting fixtures. The two laser sensors are mounted at the end of gun barrel at a distance of 10cm apart. The specimens used in this study are solid laminates made of graphite/epoxy unidirectional prepreg (HT145/RS1212, HFG) with $[0/90]_{4S}$ stacking sequence. Three PVDF sensors are attached on the upper surface of specimen in 1-direction (0°), 2-direction (90°), and diagonal-direction (45°), respectively. Each specimen was placed on a rigid support and all edges are clamped by a steel fixture. The sensor signals were recorded at a rate of 1MHz by DAQ system (PXI, NI) for the further analysis.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up and impact specimen

Sensors and Signal Processing

The PVDF film sensor (DT1-028, Measurement Specialities) with effective area A_p and thickness t_p is subjected to strains, ε_x , ε_y , and ε_z the charge developed in the film is given by Q and the corresponding open circuit voltage \bar{V} is then

$$\bar{V} = \frac{Q}{C_p} = \frac{1}{A_p} \int_{A_p} (C_x \varepsilon_x + C_y \varepsilon_y + C_z \varepsilon_z) dA \quad (1)$$

where sensor constant, C_x , C_y , and C_z are defined as

$$C_x = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{31}, \quad C_y = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{32}, \quad \text{and} \quad C_z = \frac{t_p}{\chi_{33}} e_{33}$$

and χ_{33} is the permittivity in the thickness direction, e_{31} , e_{32} , and e_{33} are the piezoelectric constants. The acoustic emission transducers (UT-1000, R-15) are peak frequencies of 152KHz and 503KHz, respectively which are connected to PAC (Physical Acoustics Cooperation), Disp-4 System.

The short time Fourier transform and wavelet transform were used to decompose the measured sensors signals. It calculates the local spectral density using windowing techniques to analyze a small section of the signal at a time. However, it is impossible to achieve high resolution in both time and frequency, simultaneously. The STFT is defined as follows:

$$STFT(\tau, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) g(t - \tau) e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (2)$$

where $g(t)$ is short time window and $x(t)$ is signal.

The wavelet basis function is localized in both time and frequency, it can act as multiscale bandpass filters, when convoluted with the signal data. The continuous wavelet transform is defined as follows:

$$W_{\Psi_x}(a, b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) \Psi^* \left(\frac{t-b}{a} \right) dt = \langle \Psi(a, b), x(t) \rangle \quad (3)$$

where a and b are scale and shift parameters, respectively. The wavelet transform indicates the similarity between the signal $x(t)$ and the shifts, scales of an elementary function.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The numerical analysis (FEA) is also performed to compare the damage initiation, failure mode, and extent of damage with the measured sensor signals. The commercial explicit nonlinear finite element analysis code for layered shell element are used to simulate the high-velocity impact event for modeling progressive failure of composite materials using typical failure criterions. The composite laminates is modeled by layered shell elements and impactor is modeled as rigid sphere and the Hashin failure criterion (Eq. (4)) are used in this study. The stiffness of each lamina assume to be zero once the lamina failed according to the failure criterion.

$$\text{Fiber failure : } \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_A} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 > 0, \quad |\sigma_1| \geq X_C \quad \text{if } \sigma_1 < 0 \quad (4.a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Matrix failure: } & \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_A} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_2 > 0, \\ & \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S_T} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T} \right) - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_2}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_A} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad \text{if } \sigma_2 < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.b)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sensor Signal Processing

The PVDF sensor signals are recorded during impact and the measured signals with different impact energies are analyzed. The PVDF sensor signals and AE signals show higher frequency signal component relevant to impact damage. The STFT and WT analysis was performed after high bypass filtering process (10KHz high pass filter). Figs. 2 and 3 show results of STFT, WT analysis of PVDF sensor signals for 2 different impact energies. The PVDF sensor signal responds to not only the multiple impact but also stress wave due to the matrix cracking, some delamination, and fiber breakage. Major damage initiation process occurred around 0.0-0.5ms as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The PVDF sensor signals show higher frequency components above 500KHz for the conditions greater than 10.0J impact energy level. These higher frequency signals may come from stress wave signals due to not only delamination but also some fiber breakage. However, to this time, it is not clear to identify quantitatively the damage modes and severity from the PVDF sensor signals but the frequency spectrum shows that the characteristics of these dominant frequencies are related with the damage mode and impact energy.

Post Impact Damage Assessment

The post impact surface appearance was shown in Fig. 4. The ultrasonic C-scan was performed using a ultrasonic C-scan system with 5 MHz transducer (Parametric). The C-scan sampling rate was set to 64MHz.

Figure 2. Short time Fourier transform for PVDF sensor signals (10KHz high pass filtered)

(a) Impact energy: 10.0 J

(b) Impact energy: 30.4 J

Figure 3. Continuous wavelet transform for PVDF sensor signals (10KHz high pass filtered)

C-scan images of amplitude measurements were recorded for each sample. The extent of the internal delaminations can be seen to be much larger than the visible top surface damage in all case. All of the delaminations were observed not only near the matrix cracks of the bottom surface but also near the top surface. Matrix cracks on the bottom surface were observed for the conditions above the 10J of impact energy. The Impact damage through the thickness in Fig.5. Comparisons of damage area by FEA with Ultrasonic C-scan of Gr/Ep specimen are examined for different impact energy.

Figure 4. Impact damage on front/back face Figure 5. Impact damage in thickness dir.

CONCLUSIONS

An impact monitoring system based on the use of a discrete number of sensor requires an efficient signal process algorithm that can detect impact damage from the sensor signal. The damage detection method for the damage-induced high-velocity impact of graphite/epoxy laminates using PVDF film sensor signals was examined. In this study, the behaviors of composite laminates subjected to high-velocity impact are analyzed using the specific wave-forms of PVDF sensor signals and AE sensor signals implying the damage initiation and propagation are monitored. Finally, the damage-induced impact behaviors verified using the explicit non-linear finite element analysis. This research demonstrates how two different sensing techniques can be used to detect and

characterize high-velocity impact damage in advanced composites. The major conclusions from this study are as follows;

- 1) The signals of PVDF sensors and AE sensors are simultaneously measured during impact event and examined to characterize the damage-induced impact behavior of composite laminates. Signal processing of sensor signal shows the possibility of correlating the extent of high-velocity impact damage, failure modes with sensor signals.
- 2) It is necessary to investigate the characteristic of damage signals for each failure mode and extent during impact process and correlate the PVDF sensor signals with acoustic emission signals quantitatively.

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